

Facile synthesis of cobalt phosphate as an electrode material for supercapacitor application

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Abstract

The amorphous cobalt phosphates with superior electrochemical performances are achieved via sonochemical method and followed by calcination. The structural crystallinity and surface purity of as synthesized cobalt phosphates are clearly examined via X-ray diffraction and FTIR spectrum. The surface morphology revealed the shape and size of the metal phosphate with respect to sonication process and calcination temperature. The electrochemical studies revealed the maximum specific capacity of 203.4 C/g is achieved with longer cyclic life (92 %) upto 2000 cycles. Therefore, these results conclude that the cobalt phosphate will play a vital role in energy storage application.

Keywords: Cobalt phosphate: Sonication process: Surface morphology: Electrochemical study